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European Health Data & Evidence Network

WP3 – Personalized Medicine

D3.7 First Report on the implementation of selected use cases in the data network

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DEFINITIONS

Participants of the EHDEN Consortium are referred to herein according to the following codes:

EMC	Erasmus Universitair Medisch Centrum Rotterdam- The Netherlands (Project Coordinator)
Synapse	Synapse Research Management Partners S.L. - Spain
UOXF	The Chancellor, Masters and Scholars of the University of Oxford - United Kingdom
UTARTU	Tartu Ulikool - Estonia
UAVR	Universidade de Aveiro – Portugal
The Hyve	The Hyve BV – the Netherlands
Odysseus	Odysseus Data Services SRO – Czech Republic
EPF	European Patients’ Forum (EPF) - Luxembourg
NICE	National Institute for Health and Care Excellence – United Kingdom
UMC	Stiftelsen WHO Collaborating Centre for International Drug Monitoring - Sweden
ICHOM	International Consortium for Health Outcomes measurement LTD - United Kingdom
Janssen	Janssen Pharmaceutica NV - Belgium (Project Lead)
Pfizer	Pfizer Limited – United Kingdom
Abbvie	AbbVie Inc - United States
IRIS	Institut De Recherches Internationales Servier - France
SARD	Sanofi Aventis Recherche & Developpement - France
Bayer	Bayer Aktiengesellschaft - Germany
Lilly	Eli Lilly and Company Limited – United Kingdom
AZ	AstraZeneca AB - Sweden
Novartis	Novartis Pharma AG - Switzerland
UCB	UCB Biopharma SPRL - Belgium
Celgene	Celgene Management SARL – Switzerland
BI	Boehringer Ingelheim International GmbH - Germany

Grant agreement	The agreement signed between the beneficiaries and the IMI JU for the undertaking of the EHDEN project (806968).
Project	The sum of all activities carried out in the framework of the Grant Agreement.
Consortium	The EHDEN Consortium, comprising the above-mentioned legal entities.
Consortium agreement	Agreement concluded amongst EHDEN participants for the implementation of the Grant Agreement. Such an agreement shall not affect the parties’ obligations to the Community and/or to one another arising from the Grant Agreement.

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PUBLISHABLE SUMMARY

The goal of WP3 “Personalised Medicine” is to establish a standardised process to enable personalised decision-making that can be utilised for multiple outcomes of interest and can be applied to observational healthcare data from any patient subpopulation.

The WP is implementing use cases to apply the developed methods in close collaboration with WP1 “Evidence Workflow Development” and WP5 “Data Workflow Implementation and Service Deployment”. The goal of these use cases is to drive the development of the analytical pipelines and their adoption.

Many use cases have already been described in previous WP3 deliverables ahead of the schedule as described in the Description of Action (DoA). In this deliverable on the implementation of selected use cases we briefly describe additional use cases that are being executed.

This work falls under Task 3.5 “Implementation of selected use cases in the data network” (M6-M60).

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1 INTRODUCTION

The goal of WP3 is to build analytical pipelines that can utilise all the data in the OMOP Common Data Model (CDM) for patient-level prediction (PLP), population-level effect estimation (PLE), heterogeneity of treatment effect (HTE), and disease trajectory analyses. Use cases are defined to drive the development of the analytical pipelines and their adoption. Major progress could be made in these domains early on in the project since we could build on work done by our team and others in the context of the Observational Health Data Sciences and Informatics ([OHDSI](#)) initiative. This allowed us to start running use cases already in the first year of the project, much faster than originally foreseen.

For example, in D3.1 “Selection of Use Cases for Personalised Medicine” we defined the study types in scope and already shared results of use cases in these domains on data sources mapped to the OMOP-CDM. This was driven by study-a-thons, e.g., as a proof-of-principle, we used routinely collected data to emulate a recently completed randomised controlled trial of unicompartmental vs total knee replacement, the Total or Partial Knee Arthroplasty Trial (TOPKAT)[1]. Another example from that deliverable was on assessing HTE of Angiotensin-Converting Enzyme (ACE)-inhibitors compared to Beta blockers with respect to CardioVascular Disease (CVD) events and cough events in the Truven MarketScan Commercial Claims and Encounters (CCAЕ) database.

In D3.4 and D3.6 “Second/Third Report on the Implementation of the Analytical Pipeline for Personalised Medicine” we have also described several use cases, e.g., in COVID-19 patients that resulted in pre-prints and publications [2-4], the development of a prediction model in Rheumatoid Arthritis (RA) patients driven by another study-a-thon, and more.

In this deliverable we provide an update on the RA use case and describe a number of additional use cases that have been worked on by the WP3 team in close collaboration with WP1.

2 USE CASES

2.1 Prediction modelling in Rheumatoid Arthritis patients

This study was described earlier in D3.4 and has been updated by adding a benchmark model containing age and sex. This allowed us to assess the value of the addition of other predictors in the more complex model.

Background: Rheumatoid arthritis (RA) is a common musculoskeletal disease, affecting approximately 0.5-1.0% of the adult population worldwide [5, 6]. While the management and prognosis of RA has improved in recent decades, identification of RA patients at high risk of adverse health outcomes remains a major challenge [7, 8]. Compared to the general population, patients with RA have an increased risk of treatment-related adverse events, such as cytopenia and infection, and comorbidities, such as cardiovascular disease and cancer [9-11]. Generally, periodic screening and monitoring for these adverse health outcomes throughout the course of therapy would allow for early interventions. However, with a wide range of possible adverse health outcomes, this is a challenging task. Methotrexate (MTX) has been adopted as the “anchor drug” since the 1990s [12], making it is the most common treatment for RA worldwide. MTX treatment implies screening or monitoring efficacy and side-effects, as with most disease modifying antirheumatic drugs (DMARDs). Using prediction models to evaluate patient-level risks in RA patients initiating first-line treatment of MTX monotherapy could allow clinicians to target those at high risk of adverse health outcomes for increased screening or monitoring throughout the course of treatment. We aimed to develop and validate patient-level prediction models for risk of leukopenia, pancytopenia,

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infection (serious, opportunistic, all), cardiovascular disease (myocardial infarction (MI), stroke), and cancer (colorectal, breast, uterine) in RA patients initiating first-line treatment of MTX monotherapy.

Methods: Patient data were obtained from 15 claims and electronic health record (EHR) databases mapped to the OMOP CDM across nine countries (Australia, Estonia, France, Germany, Japan, Netherlands, Spain, United Kingdom, and United States of America). All RA patients initiating first-line treatment of MTX monotherapy with at least one year of prior observation were included. Prediction models were developed on the Optum® De-identified Clinformatics® Data Mart Database (Optum Claims) using L1-regularised logistic regression to estimate the risk of adverse health outcomes in three months (leukopenia, pancytopenia, infection), two years (MI and stroke), and 5 years (cancer) after treatment initiation. This allowed us to develop the models on approximately 20,000 RA patients, with 75% and 25% of the data used for training and testing the models, respectively. Candidate predictors included five-year age groups, sex, and past medical history. For each outcome, two L1-regularised logistic regression models were developed: 1) one model using all candidate predictors for a data-driven approach of predictor selection, and 2) one model using only age groups and sex as candidate predictors to provide a benchmark. More than 131,000 RA patients from the other 14 databases were included for external validation. Performance was assessed using the area under the receiver operator characteristic curve (AUROC) and calibration plots.

Results: For uterine cancer, the final study population contained less than 25 RA patients with an outcome event which is too small for a meaningful analysis. For leukopenia, the AUROC was below 0.6, indicating modest discrimination. For pancytopenia, no predictors were identified for both the data-driven approach and the benchmark, and we were therefore unable to develop any prediction model for this outcome. For opportunistic infection, and all infection, the AUROCs were also below 0.6. For colorectal cancer and breast cancer, the AUROCs were below 0.65. We did not consider the internal validation AUROC < 0.65 high enough to warrant validating the model externally. Therefore, these outcomes were omitted from further analysis. However, for risk of serious infections, MI, and stroke, we were able to develop data-driven models that showed good performance on internal and external validation. Internal validation resulted in AUROCs of 0.743 (0.684-0.801), 0.764 (0.721-0.808), and 0.770 (0.729-0.810), respectively, indicating good discrimination. The large sample size of the development dataset allowed for adequate calibration as expected. External validation results showed good discrimination and adequate calibration across other databases, although for some databases the AUROC confidence intervals were wide because of few outcome events (see Table 1). In databases where the outcome incidence is substantially higher or lower than in the development database, the models may benefit from recalibration. Overall, the data-driven models for risk of serious infections, MI, and stroke demonstrated transportability to RA patients from 14 other databases.

Conclusions: To the best of our knowledge, our study is the first to develop and externally validate patient-level prediction models for risk of a variety of adverse health outcomes in RA patients initiating first-line treatment of MTX monotherapy. The models developed and internally validated for serious infection, MI, and stroke using a large-scale USA claims database (Optum Claims) showed good performance across multiple claims and EHR databases, where the data-driven approach of predictor selection consistently outperformed the benchmark and can be studied for clinical use. The models had particularly good external validation performance on the USA databases and appeared to perform well (with wider confidence intervals) on the international databases, too. RA patients identified at high risk of serious infection, MI, or stroke could be targeted for increased screening or monitoring throughout the course of treatment, complementary to current screening or monitoring strategies. In this way, the models may enable clinicians to provide better personalised care to RA patients initiating first-line MTX monotherapy.

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Published Outputs: A full manuscript detailing the developed prediction models is currently under review for publication in a high impact journal.

Results Explorer (Shiny App): <https://data.ohdsi.org/EhdenRaPrediction/>

Table 1. Internal (Optum Claims) and external validation results.

Outcome	Database	RA patients	RA patients with outcome event (%)	Data-driven approach (age groups, sex, conditions, drugs) - AUC (95% CI)	Benchmark (age groups, sex) - AUC (95% CI)
Serious infection	Optum Claims	21,276	316 (1.5)	0.743 (0.684-0.801)	0.682 (0.621-0.744)
	Estonia	1,441	8 (0.6)	0.828 (0.640-1.000)	0.760 (0.657-0.864)
	SIDIAP-H	2,051	5 (0.2)	0.784 (0.649-0.918)	0.762 (0.580-0.944)
	Optum EHR	29,980	308 (1.0)	0.760 (0.734-0.787)	0.632 (0.599-0.664)
	JMDC	4,871	15 (0.3)	0.718 (0.617-0.820)	0.627 (0.506-0.748)
	MDCR	6,662	154 (2.3)	0.665 (0.621-0.709)	0.593 (0.547-0.638)
	CCAE	29,303	223 (0.8)	0.648 (0.612-0.685)	0.543 (0.506-0.581)
	MDCD	3,793	123 (3.2)	0.626 (0.578-0.675)	0.498 (0.442-0.554)
	IQVIA US Hospital	3,871	776 (20.0)	0.616 (0.594-0.638)	0.559 (0.536-0.581)
Myocardial infarction	Optum Claims	21,463	417 (1.9)	0.764 (0.721-0.808)	0.720 (0.677-0.762)
	IPCI	1,458	24 (1.6)	0.819 (0.717-0.920)	0.782 (0.720-0.844)
	Optum EHR	30,568	466 (1.5)	0.748 (0.726-0.771)	0.711 (0.689-0.733)
	IQVIA LPD France	2,652	5 (0.2)	0.735 (0.597-0.874)	0.505 (0.264-0.745)
	SIDIAP-H	2,057	17 (0.8)	0.724 (0.607-0.841)	0.654 (0.539-0.768)
	IQVIA US Ambul	28,129	114 (0.4)	0.722 (0.675-0.769)	0.662 (0.622-0.702)
	MDCD	3,876	88 (2.3)	0.694 (0.634-0.754)	0.609 (0.553-0.666)
	CCAE	29,509	186 (0.6)	0.685 (0.643-0.727)	0.649 (0.615-0.683)
	MDCR	6,739	218 (3.2)	0.672 (0.635-0.709)	0.572 (0.533-0.611)
	IQVIA Germany	8,046	39 (0.5)	0.670 (0.570-0.770)	0.510 (0.415-0.606)
	IQVIA US Hospital	4,331	190 (4.4)	0.650 (0.611-0.689)	0.597 (0.560-0.634)
	Estonia	1,455	18 (1.2)	0.623 (0.480-0.767)	0.712 (0.610-0.814)
	JMDC	4,899	12 (0.2)	0.591 (0.436-0.745)	0.588 (0.402-0.773)
	IQVIA THIN	7,850	51 (0.6)	0.587 (0.503-0.672)	0.639 (0.579-0.699)
	IQVIA Australia	359	7 (1.9)	0.563 (0.288-0.837)	0.624 (0.451-0.797)
	Stroke	Optum Claims	21,425	527 (2.5)	0.770 (0.729-0.810)
IPCI		1,467	6 (0.4)	0.949 (0.903-0.994)	0.817 (0.651-0.984)
Optum EHR		30,506	517 (1.7)	0.790 (0.770-0.810)	0.735 (0.714-0.755)
IQVIA Germany		8,052	41 (0.5)	0.778 (0.697-0.859)	0.646 (0.567-0.725)
MDCD		3,864	129 (3.3)	0.777 (0.737-0.817)	0.685 (0.641-0.730)
Estonia		1,455	23 (1.6)	0.750 (0.672-0.829)	0.723 (0.641-0.810)
JMDC		4,899	32 (0.7)	0.746 (0.647-0.844)	0.644 (0.548-0.741)
SIDIAP-H		2,057	23 (1.1)	0.722 (0.633-0.812)	0.708 (0.623-0.792)
IQVIA US Ambul		28,163	115 (0.4)	0.711 (0.666-0.757)	0.684 (0.645-0.723)
CCAE		29,509	259 (0.9)	0.704 (0.670-0.738)	0.639 (0.610-0.667)
MDCR		6,734	304 (4.5)	0.673 (0.642-0.705)	0.575 (0.542-0.608)
IQVIA THIN		7,852	23 (0.3)	0.663 (0.562-0.764)	0.646 (0.547-0.745)
IQVIA US Hospital		4,306	208 (4.8)	0.630 (0.591-0.668)	0.621 (0.585-0.658)

2.2 Validation of existing Dementia prediction models

Background: Many dementia prediction models have been developed, but only few have been externally validated, which hinders clinical uptake and may pose a risk if models are applied to patients regardless. Replicating and externally validating a prediction model is a difficult task, where we mostly rely on the completeness of model reporting in a published article. We aimed to assess reporting of existing dementia prediction models for external validation and externally validated a subset of models.

Methods: We identified dementia prediction models that were developed between 2011 – 2020 and assessed if they could be replicated given a set of external validation criteria. In addition, we replicated

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three of these models (Walters' Dementia Risk Score, Mehta's RxDx-Dementia Risk Index, and Nori's ADRD dementia prediction model) and externally validated them on six observational health databases from the United States, United Kingdom, Germany and the Netherlands.

Results: Commonly reported information for replicating a model includes the prediction method, development database, target and outcome definitions (Table 2). Less frequently reported are model-specific properties such as predictor definitions including the time window in which a predictor is assessed, predictor coefficients, the baseline hazard or intercept, and the time-at-risk.

Table 2. Reporting of validation criteria in reviewed studies that are useful for model replication and validation. In total we reviewed 59 models for dementia prediction.

Category	Validation criteria	No. of models (%)
Population settings	Target population definition	59 (100)
	Index date	23 (39)
	Time-at-risk	39 (66)
	Outcome definition	59 (100)
Statistical analysis settings	Prediction method	59 (100)
	Predictor definitions	46 (78)
	Predictor time window	21 (36)
	Model specifications: Full model	8 (14)
	Model specifications: Partial model	19 (32)

In Table 3, the replicated model by Walters (development c-statistic: 0.84) showed satisfactory transportability (0.67 – 0.75 c-statistic). The Mehta model (development c-statistic: 0.81) transported well to some of the external databases (0.69 – 0.79 c-statistic). The Nori model (development AUROC: 0.69) transported well (0.62 – 0.68 AUROC), but performed modestly overall.

Table 3. Internal and external discrimination performance in AUROC/c-statistic of externally validated models.

Model	Development database	MDCR	IQGER	OPSES	OPEHR	CPRD	IPCI	IMRD
Walters	0.84 (THIN)	0.69 (0.69 – 0.69)*	0.75 (0.75 – 0.75)*	0.74 (0.74 – 0.74)*	0.73 (0.73 – 0.73)*	0.67 (0.66 – 0.67)*	0.76 (0.75 – 0.77)*	0.68 (0.68 – 0.69)*, †
Mehta	0.81 (CPRD)	0.69 (0.69 – 0.70)	0.72 (0.71 – 0.72)	0.71 (0.70 – 0.71)	0.73 (0.73 – 0.73)	0.79 (0.78 – 0.80)†	0.78 (0.76 – 0.80)	0.79 (0.78 – 0.80)
Nori	0.69 (Optum)	0.66 (0.66 – 0.67)	0.67 (0.66 – 0.68)	0.67 (0.66 – 0.68)	0.62 (0.62 – 0.63)†	0.68 (0.67 – 0.69)	0.64 (0.62 – 0.67)	0.68 (0.68 – 0.69)

*Discrimination AUROC/c-statistic (95% confidence intervals); †Validation of the replicated model in the original development database (or an approximation of it)

Recalibration showed improvements for the Walters and Nori models, while recalibration could not be assessed for the Mehta model due to unreported baseline hazard.

Conclusion: Model reporting is mostly insufficient and more explicit reporting could improve validation efforts. Authors should be held accountable to validate their models and develop and report them in a way that enables easier model replication. Replicated models showed good transportability to some databases, however, certain aspects could not be replicated, because they were insufficiently or only vaguely reported.

This work is currently under submission.

2.3 Prediction model development and validation for Dementia

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As an addition to the replication study presented above we are currently working on the development and validation of a new model.

Introduction: Early diagnosis of individuals at high risk of dementia allows for improved care and risk factor-targeted intervention. [13] Many patient-level prediction models for identifying individuals who are at risk of dementia have been developed, but few have been externally validated. [14-16] In our previous work we hypothesised that the lack of validation can be attributed to model reporting, which does not allow for model replication and validation, and in turn may limit clinical uptake. In this study we aim to develop and validate patient-level models to predict late-life dementia in the general population across a network of observational databases.

Methods: This study used observational data from administrative claims and electronic health records. The five databases included were mapped into the Observational Medical Outcomes Partnership Common Data Model (OMOP CDM).[17]

We included people between 50-79 years of age with an index date between 1.1.2012 - 31.12.2014. We use the latest outpatient visit (OP) or visit to the general practitioner (GP) as the index event, depending on the origin of the data.

We investigate the outcome within five years following the index date. The outcome is defined as a record of dementia (concept 4182210) and all its hierarchical descendants according to the SNOMED vocabulary. The results of this study will be reported in a publication and the next use case deliverable in WP3 (D3.9).

2.4 Development and validation of a model to predict coagulopathy in unvaccinated COVID-19

This study was performed as part of a project for the European Medicines Agency (ENCePP study: [EUPAS40414](#)).

Introduction: Prediction models that combine various patient features can be used to estimate individuals' personalised risks of adverse outcomes in COVID-19. A prediction model of thromboembolic events among patients with COVID-19 is lacking. If available and with good performance, such models would be a valuable tool in the management of COVID-19. Numerous prediction models have been developed for COVID-19, but many have been limited by small sample sizes, a lack of representative study populations, and an absence of external validation [18]. Using routinely-collected data can offer a solution to these potential issues, especially when using data mapped to a common data model which would allow for the development and external validation of models to be done in both a timely and reproducible manner [19].

The aim of this study is to develop and externally validate prediction models for venous thromboembolic events (VTE) and arterial thromboembolic events (ATE) for patients with COVID-19 (who have not received a vaccine).

Methods: We used the patient-level prediction framework for model development and validation [19]. This framework enables the development of analysis packages in R that can be shared across data sites mapped to the OMOP CDM. Figure 1 illustrates the modeling approach used to predict each of the outcomes given a set of predictors from the condition and drug domain, recorded in an observation window prior to the index date. Three models were planned per protocol:

- Baseline models, including only age and sex
- Parsimonious models: based on age, sex and pre-specified risk factors

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- Data-driven models, including all potential comorbidities and medicines use available in the utilised databases, and selected using regularisation. (The data-driven model is still under development and no results are ready to be shared for this report.)

Figure 1. Patient-level prediction of outcome in a time window following the index date using predictors from the condition and drug domain.

We included persons of any age with an index date between 1 September 2020 – 1 March 2021. The index event is either a positive COVID-19 PCR test or a condition diagnosis of COVID-19. We excluded patients that had any prior vaccination for COVID-19.

We investigated six clinical outcomes within a time-at-risk of 30 days. The outcomes predicted were myocardial infarction, ischemic stroke, a combined outcome of myocardial infarction or ischemic stroke, pulmonary embolism, deep vein thrombosis, and venous thromboembolism.

We used a train-test split by person to perform internal validation. Each person appeared only once in the datasets, because we only used their earliest index date. In the development cohort, a random sample of 75% of patients was used to develop the prediction models and the remaining 25% of patients were used to internally validate the models. We trained models using LASSO regularised logistic regression with three-fold cross validation to learn the optimal regularisation hyperparameter through an adaptive search.

To evaluate the performance, we estimated the discrimination of the model using the area under the receiver operating characteristic curve (AUROC) and the model calibration (Eavg and age-sex stratified observed vs expected risk plot). The AUROC indicated the probability that for two randomly selected patients, the patient who gets the outcome will be assigned a higher risk. The model calibration was presented in a plot to examine agreement between predicted and observed risk across deciles (or centiles) of predicted risk. Calibration was assessed using Eavg, a single value metric, which is the average absolute difference between observed and predicted probabilities (where smaller values are better) [20].

For each dataset, models were developed in a training set based on the CPRD AURUM UK primary care data, and evaluated in (1) the test set, (2) subset of the test set with age below 65 years, (3) subset of the test set with age 65 and above, (4) female subset of the test set, and (5) male subset of the test set. To perform external validation, we applied the models to identical settings across the other available primary care data sources not used for development of the model: IPCI Netherlands, and SIDIAP PADRIS from Spain. Evaluation in the external data source was performed on the full data set, since no train-test split was required.

Importantly, we recalibrated the models for each external database using mean calibration (or also referred to as calibration-in-the-large). Mean calibration adjusts the average predicted risk to the observed event rate by using a correction factor based upon the difference between those two. In addition, the intercept is

adjusted. As a result, if we were to underpredict the risk in the external population, the factor will increase the risk by some amount, and vice versa for overprediction [21].

These analyses were conducted and reported according to the Transparent Reporting of a multivariate prediction model for Individual Prediction or Diagnosis (TRIPOD) guidelines and adhered to the open science principles for publicly pre-specifying and tracking changes to study objects, protocol and code as described in the book of OHDSI. See also the EHDEN Academy [course](#) on Patient-Level Prediction.

Results: Models were attempted for VTE and its subcomponents DVT and PE separately. Baseline (age-sex only) and parsimonious (age, sex and pre-specified risk factors in the previous section) achieved similar performance for all VTE and ATE outcomes in internal validation, as demonstrated in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Internal validation performance on development database CPRD AURUM: AUROC discrimination with 95% Confidence Intervals (top) and Eavg calibration performance (bottom).

As shown, baseline models for VTE had good discrimination (AUC 0.80), and the addition of pre-specified risk factors did not improve this despite increasing complexity. Discrimination was similar in men (AUC 0.77) vs women (AUC 0.82) and in COVID-19 patients aged <65 (AUC 0.80), but declined quite significantly in older ages >=65 (AUC 0.52). Discrimination was better for PE (AUC 0.77 in baseline, 0.78 in parsimonious models) than for DVT (AUC 0.67 and 0.66).

Calibration was good as demonstrated by low Eavg values in Figure 2, and we observed good correlation between expected and observed risk in most age-sex strata.

External validation of both baseline and parsimonious models are reported in Figure 3 (IPCI, NL) and Figure 4 (SIDIAP, ES). Results were similar to those seen in the internal validation.

Figure 3. External validation performance: AUROC discrimination and Eavg calibration results from IPCI (NL).

Figure 4. External validation performance: AUROC discrimination and Eavg calibration results from SIDIAP (ES).

Conclusion: Prediction models developed on CPRD Aurum for VTE and ATE perform well on external databases IPCI and SIDIAP. However, all models perform poorly on patients aged 65 and above. Additional results for fully data-driven models, which may show different performances than the baseline and parsimonious models, will be available in the future.

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2.5 Treatment heterogeneity in comparative effectiveness of teriparatide vs bisphosphonates

This work was presented as a poster at the 2021 OHDSI global symposium (<https://www.ohdsi.org/2021-global-symposium-showcase-95/>).

Background: Bisphosphonates are first line treatments to prevent osteoporotic fractures. Teriparatide has been recently shown to be more effective in a head-to-head RCT, and is currently used for more severe cases.

Aim: Our primary aim is to compare overall effectiveness of teriparatide and oral bisphosphonates using observational data mapped to OMOP-CDM. As a secondary objective we want to assess how these effects vary across the distribution of baseline hip fracture risk, as current guidelines target treatment with teriparatide to higher risk patients due to its high cost.

Methods: Network new user cohort study using databases mapped to the OMOP common data model. We included subjects aged >50, registered for 1+ year, initiating treatment with bisphosphonate/s or teriparatide. The main outcome of interest is hip fracture. We used large scale propensity scores for 1:4 matching to minimise confounding by indication. Models for the prediction of hip fracture risk were developed and validated in all databases. We conducted overall and risk-quartile stratified analyses. We checked covariate imbalance (overall and for each risk stratum) excluding analyses with severe residual imbalance after matching. Finally, a total of 129 negative control outcomes were included to calibrate for residual confounding. Cox regression was used to estimate calibrated hazard ratios (HR) and Kaplan-Meier estimate differences on day 730 to estimate absolute effects. We provide meta-analytic estimates for the overall analysis and for the top quartile of risk.

Results: This is ongoing research. Early analyses were performed in IBM MarketScan® Medicare Supplemental Database (MDCR), Optum® De-Identified Clinformatics Data Mart Database – Date of Death (OptumDOD) and Optum® de-identified Electronic Health Record Dataset (Optum-EHR). We included a total of 5,061 and 18,322 users of teriparatide and bisphosphonates from MDCR, 4,205 and 15,953 from OptumDOD, and 5,301 and 18,872 from Optum-EHR. Overall HRs were 0.94 [0.76-1.18], 0.80 [0.65-0.99] and 0.92 [0.71-1.21] respectively, with meta-analytic HR of 0.88 [0.77-1.00]; I²=0%. We found evidence of residual confounding in quartiles 1-3 of predicted risk, but no identifiable imbalances in the top quartile of risk in all three databases. HRs for the top risk quartile were 0.83 [0.64-1.08], 0.74 [0.57-0.95] and 0.84 [0.62-1.14] (meta-analytic HR 0.80 [0.69-0.93]), with two-year absolute risk reductions of 1.23% [-0.15% to 2.62%], 1.61% [0.30% to 2.93%], and 0.31% [-0.74% to 1.35%] respectively. Meta-analytic HR for top risk quartile 0.80 [0.68-0.93]; I²=0%.

Conclusion: This is the first observational study assessing teriparatide in a set of fracture endpoints compared to oral bisphosphonates users in postmenopausal women using multiple large real-world databases. Our findings are in line with previous trials and suggest a 12% relative risk reduction of hip fracture with teriparatide compared to bisphosphonates. A slightly stronger effect was seen amongst highest risk patients, where relative risk reduction was of 20%, with absolute risk reductions ranging from 0.3% to 1.6%. We intend to expand our analyses to include data from IBM MarketScan® Commercial Database, IBM MarketScan® Multi-State Medicaid Database and PharMetrics Plus. Finally, we intend to consider two additional stratification schemes: a 25-75% split, focusing on the patients at the top quarter of baseline risk, and a stratification based on existing guidelines.

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2.6 Risk of death 0 to 30 days after hospitalisation for COVID-19

A clinical use case on the risk of death 0 to 30 days after hospitalisation for COVID-19 was performed as part of a publication on the framework we have developed [2].

Background and Objective: As a response to the ongoing COVID-19 pandemic, several prediction models have been rapidly developed, with the aim of providing evidence-based guidance. However, no COVID-19 prediction model in the existing literature has been found to be reliable. Models are commonly assessed to have a risk of bias, often due to insufficient reporting, use of non-representative data, and lack of large-scale external validation. In this paper, we present the Observational Health Data Sciences and Informatics (OHDSI) analytics pipeline for patient-level prediction as a standardised approach for rapid yet reliable development and validation of prediction models. We demonstrate how our analytics pipeline and open-source software can be used to answer important prediction questions while limiting potential causes of bias (e.g., by validating phenotypes, specifying the target population, performing large-scale external validation and publicly providing all analytical source code).

Methods: We show step-by-step how to implement the pipeline for the question: ‘In patients hospitalised with COVID-19, what is the risk of death 0 to 30 days after hospitalisation’. We develop models using six different machine learning methods in the Optum© De-Identified Clinformatics® Data Mart US claims database containing over 20,000 COVID-19 hospitalisations and externally validate the models using data containing over 45,000 COVID-19 hospitalisations from South Korea, Spain, and the US.

Results: Our open-source tools enabled us to efficiently go end-to-end from problem design to reliable model development and evaluation. When predicting death in patients hospitalised for COVID-19 adaBoost, random forest, gradient boosting machine, and decision tree yielded similar or lower internal and external validation discrimination performance compared to L1-regularised logistic regression, whereas the MLP neural network consistently resulted in lower discrimination. L1-regularised logistic regression models were well calibrated.

Conclusion: Our results show that following the OHDSI analytics pipeline for patient-level prediction can enable the rapid development towards reliable prediction models. The OHDSI tools and pipeline are open source and available to researchers around the world.

3 NEXT STEPS

WP3 is progressing faster than expected and that has led to the implementation of more use cases than originally foreseen. These use cases are important to continue to drive the agile development of the analytical pipelines but are also very valuable to onboard the new Data Partners in the evolving EHDEN ecosystem. In the next period there will be an emphasis on evidence-A-Thons that aim to establish the research readiness of the Data Partner teams that is needed for future network studies. In these focussed meetings the Data Partners will collaborate with others to execute a use case in close collaboration with EHDEN experts. These have proven to be very valuable to better understand the power of the analytical tools to generate reliable evidence on their data.

In addition, we will organise study-A-Thons which are meetings that bring together a multidisciplinary team of clinicians, informaticians, data scientists, academic clinicians, epidemiologists, and patient representatives, and OMOP-CDM experts that collaboratively design and execute impactful studies. Good examples of those are the [Oxford Study-a-Thon](#), the [Barcelona Study-a-Thon](#), the [COVID-19 Study-a-Thon](#), and more recently the [IMI Pioneer Study-a-Thon](#). Based on experience of these study-a-

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thons, a number of insights have been generated to optimally conduct future research events, and to assist the wider research community with establishing their own study-a-thons, incorporating standardised data and standardised analytical tools.

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